

SYNTHETIC GONADOGENS. PART I

By S. M. MUKHERJI, R. P. GANDHI AND V. S. GAIND

The synthesis of 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-19-octalone-2 and 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-8-ethyl-19-octalone-2 as potential androgens is described herein.

The recent discovery of highly androgenic activity in 19-nor-testosterone (Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 367; cf. Wilds and Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5366), 19-nor-17 α -methyltestosterone (Djerassi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 4092) and 18-nor-D₂ homo-androstane-3:17 α -dione (Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4866), and progestational activity in 19-nor-progesterone (Djerassi, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4440) suggests the desirability of examining for androgenic or progestational activity the hydroaromatic structures conveniently obtained by the Birch reduction (Birch and Mukherji, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2531, and references cited therein) of the phenolic compounds which have already proved to be estrogenic. It may be pointed out further that while Dodds *et al.* (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1959, B127, 140; cf. Salzer, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1942, 274, 39) recorded (I) as having estrogenic activity, Wilds and Hoffman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3266) reported androgenic activity in the analogous hydroaromatic substances (II).

Novello and Christy (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 5431) recorded estrogenic activity of 3-(6'-hydroxy-2'-naphthyl)-cyclohex-2-enone (III).

Blanchard, Stuart and Tallman (*Endocrinology*, 1943, 32, 307) and Madaeva *et al.* (*Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1953, 23, 472; *Chem. Abst.*, 1954, 48, 5136) reported highly estrogenic activity respectively of 2:4-di-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-3-ethylhexane (IV) and 3:5-bis-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-methylpent-4-ene (V).

The above findings of estrogenic activity in the structure (IV) and (V) are rather surprising and cast some doubts on the stereo-relationship of the functional groups in natural and synthetic estrogens. Although these structures preserve the superficial skeletal resemblance with the natural steroid hormone structures, when written in the distended form as shown, they appear to represent a development away from the structures of steroids and towards the simpler, yet no less potent, substances in which even the functional groups do not conform to the original spatial relationship.

The structure such as (IV) could be trimmed and the middle aliphatic chain coiled into ring B (steroid). The analogous hydroaromatic structures would then become of considerable interest for eventual androgenic or progestational activity. With this end in view we have synthesised 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-1:9-octalone-2 (XI) and 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-8-ethyl-1:9-octalone-2 (XV) along the following scheme:

The starting material, α -(*p*-anisyl)- β -(*p*-anisoyl)-propionic acid (VI) was prepared by the method of Dalal, Bokil and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1939, 8, 190). But unlike these workers we could not raise the yield to more than 55% with tetrachloroethane as the solvent. In nitrobenzene and carbon disulphide as the solvents, the yields were more disappointing. In course of the preparation of *p*-anisylsuccinic acid, we have improved the yield in the Knoevenagel-Cope condensation of *p*-anisaldehyde with ethyl cyanoacetate to 100%, whereas the previously reported yield was only 77% (Baker and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 560) (see Experimental).

The acid (VI) furnished a hydrazone, but the reduction of the keto group proved to be difficult. Because of low solubility in toluene it could not be reduced by Martin's modification of the Clemmensen reduction. The Wolff-Kishner reduction by Huang-Minlon's technique (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2487) also did not provide satisfactory results. Among the various combinations of the base and solvent tried to effect reduction, may be mentioned: sodium ethoxide in glycol, sodium diethyleneglycolate in diethyleneglycol, sodium in benzyl alcohol and potassium hydroxide in diethyleneglycol.

The keto-acid (VI) was then converted in 92% yield into its methyl ester (VII) to effect its solubilisation in toluene. The Clemmensen reduction by Martin's modification then proceeded smoothly to furnish methyl α , γ -di-(*p*-anisyl)-butyrate (VIII) in 75% yield. A similar procedure in the Clemmensen reduction of compounds resisting reduction had earlier been recorded by Haworth and Mavin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2720) and Fieser and Peters (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4373). However, during the Clemmensen reduction of the ester (VII), considerable demethylation took place. The crude reduction product was therefore methylated, prior to distillation, with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone. Hydrolysis of the reduced ester (VIII) did not proceed satisfactorily either. The ester (VIII) was therefore cyclised in 70% yield to 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-anisyl)-1 tetralone (IX) by means of polyphosphoric acid. The ketone (IX), thus obtained initially as a viscous oil, solidified after a few days, and it was characterised through its 2:4-dinitrophenyl-

hydrazone. The Clemmensen reduction of the ketone (IX) by Martin's modification for 60 hours, followed by methylation of the crude product, furnished 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-anisyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (X) in good yield. This was then subjected to the Birch reduction process as modified by Wilds and Nelson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360). The resulting tetrahydro derivative on hydrolysis afforded 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-1:9-octalone-2 (XI). This ketone exhibited a strong absorption band at $220\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 9879) in alcohol. It was characterised by its deep red *bis*-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The presence of two ethylenic bonds in the structure (XI) was further established by catalytic hydrogenation with palladium-charcoal catalyst (5%) when almost theoretical volume (95%) of hydrogen was absorbed and a fully hydrogenated system (XII) was obtained which yielded a yellow *bis*-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. Catalytic hydrogenation of polycyclic $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones of type (XI) generally leads to the formation of the *cis*-isomer of the saturated ketones (Cornforth and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1855), although there are cases in which the *trans*-isomer or a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of the reduced ketones has been obtained (Butenandt *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 2094, 2097). Our product (XII), however, has been provisionally designated as the *cis*-isomer.

7-Methoxy-2-(*p*-anisyl)-1-tetralone (IX) was allowed to react with an excess of ethylmagnesium bromide. The resulting carbinol (XIII) was not, however, isolated, because on distillation it underwent spontaneous dehydration, which was facilitated by the presence of a trace of iodine to furnish in 72% yield 7-methoxy-1-ethyl-2-(*p*-anisyl)-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (XIV) in a crystalline form. The product (XIV) was then reduced with lithium and ethyl alcohol in liquid ammonia as before. The resulting hexahydro derivative was hydrolysed as in the case of (XI). 7-(4'-Ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-8-ethyl-1:9-octalone-2 (XV), thus obtained, was characterised by its absorption in the ultraviolet range at $222\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 10230) in alcohol, and through its deep red *bis*-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Attempts at obtaining the diketones (XI) and (XV) in crystalline form by regenerating them for the respective 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones were not successful. Analogous structures, which have been synthesised by Bentley and Firth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2398, 2403), while our work was almost completed, are also reported to be liquids at ordinary temperatures.

Biological assessment of the two compounds (XI) and (XV) is in hand.

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl α -Cyano- β -(p-anisyl)-acrylate.—A solution of *p*-anisaldehyde (54.4 g., 0.4M), ethyl cyanoacetate (45.2 g., 0.4M), piperidine (1.7 g., 0.02M), acetic acid (6 g., 0.1M) and anhydrous benzene (140 c.c.) were taken in a flask connected to a modified Dean and Stark water separator and heated on the oil-bath at 120° - 130° till no more water separated (10 hours). The content was then poured on crushed ice when the yellow solid separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with benzene. The crude solid product was dissolved in benzene and the combined benzene solution dried (Na_2SO_4).

* M.p. and b.p. are uncorrected. Analyses were carried out by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation under diminished pressure furnished an almost quantitative yield (92 g.) of the acrylic ester derivative as a light yellow product, b.p. 200° - $203^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, which solidified immediately, m.p. 84° (Baker and Lapworth, *loc cit.*, record m.p. 84°).

Methyl α -(p-anisyl) - β -(p-anisoyl)-propionate (VII).—A mixture of α -(p-anisyl)- β -(p-anisoyl)-propionic acid (VI, 18.8 g.) (Dalal, Bokil and Nargund, *loc. cit.*) anhydrous methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (7 c.c., *d* 1.84) was refluxed with exclusion of moisture for 8 hours. Most of the alcohol was then removed and the residue poured on iced water. The resulting resinous mass was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed free of acid, and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation under diminished pressure furnished 18 g. (92%) of the ester (VII) which solidified on keeping. Crystallisation from methyl alcohol afforded milk-white needles, m.p. 93° . (Found: C, 69.25; H, 6.20. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 69.50; H, 6.14) per cent.

Methyl γ -Di-(p-anisyl)-butyrate (VIII).—A mixture of amalgamated zinc wool (25 g.), water (13 c.c.), toluene (35 c.c.), HCl (36 c.c.) and the methyl ester (VII: 16 g.) was refluxed on the oil-bath, maintained at 135° - 140° , for 55 hours while HCl (conc., 8 c.c.) was added every 6 hours. The toluene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined toluene-ether extract was washed free of acid and the solvents driven off under diminished pressure. The crude residue developed an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and was therefore methylated with dimethyl sulphate (10 g.) and potassium carbonate (5 g.) in boiling acetone. After refluxing for three hours acetone was removed and the residue poured on cold water. The viscous oily substance was extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). After aspiration of the solvent, the residue on distillation yielded 11.8 g. (75%) of the reduced product (VIII), b.p. 240 - $41^{\circ}/4\text{ mm.}$, n_D^{20} , 1.5438. The ferric chloride test with the distilled product was negative. (Found: C, 71.98; H, 6.71 $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.59; H, 7.05 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-(p-anisyl)-1-tetralone (IX).—Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by heating together phosphorus pentoxide (70 g.) with 85% phosphoric acid (40 c.c.) for 2 hours at 100° with the exclusion of moisture. To the homogeneous solution was gradually added methyl γ -di-(p-anisyl)-butyrate (11.0 g.). During addition heat was evolved and the contents were occasionally cooled to maintain the temperature below 100° . The mixture was then heated on the steam-bath for additional 2 hours when a deep brown colour developed. Crushed ice was then added and the resinous extract was washed with water and 5% sodium carbonate solution and then dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent on being distilled off the residual oil on distillation under reduced pressure furnished 6.9 g. (70%) of the ketone (IX) as a colorless immobile liquid, b.p. 227 - $30^{\circ}/4\text{ mm.}$, which solidified on keeping. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished white plates, m.p. 84 - 85° . (Found: C, 76.15; H, 6.28. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 76.57; H, 6.43 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 225° . (Found: N, 11.70. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.12 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-(p-anisyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (X).—The above ketone (IX: 5.64 g.) was reduced by using amalgamated zinc wool (10 g.), HCl (conc., 13 c.c.), water (6 c.c.) and toluene (25 c.c.). Refluxing was continued for 60 hours during which period HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) was added every six hours. After working up as in the case of (VIII), the crude product was methylated with dimethyl sulphate (5 g.) and potassium carbonate (2.7 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.). On working up in the usual manner, 3.3 g. (59%) of *7-methoxy-2-(p-anisyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene* (X) was obtained as a colorless viscous substance, b.p. $210-12^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$ (Found: C, 80.40; H, 7.30. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.56; H, 7.51 per cent).

7-(4'-Keto-cyclohex-2'-enyl)-1:9-octalone-2 (XI).—To a solution of (X: 2.15 g.) in dry ether (90 c.c.) and anhydrous ammonia (150 c.c.) was added, with stirring, freshly cut lithium metal (0.89 g.) in small pieces during 6 minutes. Stirring was continued for another 5 minutes whereafter absolute ethyl alcohol (7.9 g.) was added dropwise during 10 minutes when] the blue colour disappeared completely. Towards the end of the reaction vigorous foaming ensued which was controlled by occasional suspension of stirring. Ammonia was evaporated off and distilled water (50 c.c.) was then added dropwise, followed by ether (100 c.c.) and the mixture stirred for half an hour. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The solvent was driven off from the the combined extract. The residue was hydrolysed with 10% H_2SO_4 (50 c.c.) on the steam-bath for 5 hours. The mixture was cooled and extracted with four portions of ether. The combined ethereal solution was washed free of acid with 5% sodium carbonate solution, followed by water and then dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent being removed the residue on distillation furnished 1.1 g. (55%) of the diketone (XI) as a sticky mass, b.p. $223-25^{\circ}/5\text{ mm.}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$, 220 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 9879). (Found: C, 79.00; H, 8.50. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.65; H, 8.25 per cent).

The bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the above diketone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture as deep orange crystals which changed colour on keeping, m.p. 125° (sintering at $120-21^{\circ}$). (Found: N, 18.30. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_8\text{N}_8$ requires N, 18.54 per cent).

4-[7-Keto-2-(cis ?)-decalyl]-cyclohexanone (XII).—The unsaturated ketone (XI: 0.49 g.) was subjected to catalytic hydrogenation with 5% Pd—C (50 mg.) using ethyl alcohol as the solvent. After 95% of the equivalent of two mols. of hydrogen was absorbed the reaction product was worked up in the usual way whereafter the residue on slow sublimation under reduced pressure yielded 0.41 g. of a colorless product. (Found: C, 77.15; H, 9.58. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.37; H, 9.74 per cent).

The above saturated diketone furnished a yellow bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone under the usual conditions, which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. $146-47^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 18.00. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_8\text{N}_8$ requires N, 18.42 per cent).

7-Methoxy-1-ethyl-2-(p-anisyl)-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (XIV).—To ice-cooled ethylmagnesium bromide (from 8.8 g. ethyl bromide, 1.92 g. magnesium turnings and 20 c.c. ether) was added a solution of *7-methoxy-2-(p-anisyl)-1-tetraone* (IX: 11.3 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.). After standing for 2 hours at room temperature the reaction mixture was refluxed on the steam-bath for 6 hours, then cooled and decomposed by pouring over 10% HCl. The hydrolysate was taken up in ether and the ethereal

extract was washed and dried (Na_2SO_4): After the removal of the solvent the residual oil, on distillation under reduced pressure in presence of a crystal of iodine, furnished 8.5 g. (72%) of 7-methoxy-1-ethyl-2-(*p*-anisyl)-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (XIV) as a viscous mass, b.p. $230-32^\circ/5$ mm., which solidified on keeping. Crystallisation from alcohol afforded colorless shining needles of (XIV), m.p. $99-100^\circ$. (Found: C, 81.43; H, 7.62. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.60; H, 7.53 per cent).

7-(4'-Ketocyclohex-2'-enyl)-8-ethyl-1:9-octalone-2 (XV).—The above compound (XIV: 5.8 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.) was subjected to reduction with lithium (2.52 g.) and absolute ethyl alcohol (16.4 g.) in liquid ammonia (300 c.c.) by following a similar procedure as described in the case of (XI). The resulting hydro derivative was hydrolysed with 10% H_2SO_4 (50 c.c.) and the hydrolysate taken up in ether, and the ethereal layer washed. After drying, the solvent was distilled off and the residue on distillation gave 3 g. (55%) of (XV) as a colorless liquid distilling at $220-25^\circ/5$ mm., $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ul}}$, 222 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 10230). (Found: C, 79.10; H, 8.54. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 79.37; H, 8.88 per cent).

The bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the above diketone was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and was crystallised (deep red) from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. $136-37^\circ$. (Found: N, 17.40. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_8\text{N}_8$ requires N, 17.71 per cent).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSHIARPUR.

Received April 24, 1956.